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Positive and Negative Impact of Covid-19 on Children and Older Adults

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Abstract

Over the past year, a worldwide pandemic has affected general life. The covid-19 pandemic also known as the corona virus has largely affected children and old age. Although medical literature shows that children and old age are minimally disposed to 2019-Corona virus disease, they are hit the hardest by the mental impact of this pandemic. Extensive lockdown and pre-emptive measures have isolated individuals, affected the world economy, and limited access to physical and mental healthcare. While these measures may be compulsory to minimize the spread of the virus, the harmful physical, psychological, and social effects are evident. Being quarantined in homes and health centers may impose a greater psychological load than the physical suffering caused by the virus. School closing, lack of outdoor activity, strange dietary and sleeping habits are likely to disturb children's usual lifestyle and can potentially promote monotony, anxiety, campaigning, annoyance, and varied neuropsychiatric manifestations. Meanwhile, the senior citizens are affected by both the virus, and the lockdown measures have seen the slightest benefits from these digital solutions. The age-based digital divide describes an ancient inequality in the access to, and skills to make use of, new technology.

Keywords: Covid19 pandemic, Lockdown, Quarantine, Children and Old age.

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1.1 Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has had huge effects on the daily lives of most individuals in the first half of 2020. The lockdown has brought about a sense of fear and nervousness around the globe. This phenomenon has led to short-term as well as long-term psychosocial and mental health implications for children and senior citizens. Millions of children could be negatively affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, and we anticipate that the greatest impact could be on those in poor socio-economic groups, who are already vulnerable and disadvantaged. However, some positive changes could also come out of this worldwide crisis.

1.2 Objectives

- This research paper aims to explore the positive and negative impact of covid-19 on children.
- This research paper aims to explore the positive and negative impact of covid-19 on older adults.

2.1 Research Methodology

The research design used in this study is descriptive investigate. Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular group of situations. It includes different kinds of fact-finding study and surveys.

2.2 Data collection

2.2.1 Secondary Data

The secondary data have been collected by different books reputed journal, RBI website and internet.

3.1 Impact of Covid-19 on Children

3.2 Positive Impacts

Childhood Development

Children's education is expected to be negative affected by school closures. Those children who have access to internet connection and smart phones are given the opportunity to be taught educational methods that will advantage them later in life. They could also get involved in different physical, knowledge, and creative activities during school closures that will help them to develop new skills.

Greater Awareness

Health specialists have advised parents to talk about the pandemic in detail with their kids. These include parents being honest, reassuring them and explanation what practical measures they can take to keep themselves and others secure.

Developing Relationships and Empathy

Spending time with their family could help some children to develop nearer relationships with them and being aware of the impact of the pandemic could also help children to develop more humanity and empathy, as they understand the value of human life.

Learning Nature's Value

Less traffic has led to reductions in largely pollution and noise, and there is anecdotal evidence that this has led to changes in our natural environment and provided additional opportunities for children to see, and appreciate, wild life.

3.3 Negative Impacts

Effects on Education

School closures carry high social and economic expenses for people across communities. Their impact however is mainly severe for the most vulnerable and marginalized group. These include:-

Intermittent learning.

Puzzlement and stress for teachers.

Parents not ready for distance and home schooling.

Challenges creating, maintaining, and improving distance Learning.

High economic expenses.

Health Issues

One of the main consequences of lockdowns and school closures could be that some children will not be able to engage in outdoor bodily activities, especially if they do not have access to outside space, which could increase weight problems and the disorders that are connected with them. School closures may also mean that children sit continuously for longer periods of time, for example at laptop, and this could lead to issues like back pain, eye strain and disturbed sleep.

Aggressive Behavioural Changes

Children are bound to miss interacting with their own look closely groups, and we fear that being deprived of their company for any length of time will lead to extreme behavioral changes.

Addiction to Social Media and the Internet

Due to school, college closures, many children will be actively encouraged to go online to carry on their education. They will also want to keep in touch with their peers, and this could increase their use of social media, which could distract them when they are meant to be doing school work. They could also be uncovered inappropriate content and bogus bullying.

Impact of Covid-19 on Older Adults

Older adults are more likely to have terrible outcomes from the virus. And as a result, negative impacts supersede any possible positive impacts.

The Ageing Body

The older are more afflicted with chronic rather than sensitive illnesses aside from locomotors difficulties – such as high blood-pressure, hypertension and diabetes, which need long-term medication. They are also more at hazard of cancer, renal diseases and musculoskeletal disorders, particularly arthritis. Reduced mobility during this time prevents them from seeking regular medical attention, and leaves them dependent on others.

Misinformation and Anxiety

As they are less recognizable with technology and apps, anecdotally speaking, older people are often exposed to, and fall prey to, half truths about ‘miracle cures’ for COVID-19 as well as overhyped claims, conspiracy theories, unscientific medical claims, etc. This in turn leads to panic and anxiety. Instead, we need to invest time and energy to educate our elderly family members about false news and its ill-effects, and improve their access to culturally sensitive and affordable mental health counselor.

The Digital Divide

The digital divide is a term originally used to describe the break in access to new technology which exists between different groups of people. The elderly has less right to use to technology than younger adults, but even those with access have less digital skills, and make extra limited use of the technology they do have. The problem of the digital divide among the elderly is not new and has been a point of rising scrutiny as technology has become a larger part of day-to-day life.

Social Isolation and Social Disconnection

Social isolation, social distancing, social disconnectedness, and loneliness were found to be mediated with sadness and anxiety. Cognitive skills and social support networks could help older adults to foster significant connection and sense of belongingness during isolation period.

Physical and Mental Health

Social isolation and social disconnection – a documented bidirectional and complex relationship between mental health issues and social disconnectedness, itself poses a serious public health concern among older adults particularly due to the psychosocial reasons and physiological health problems such as mental health problems, cardiovascular, autoimmune, neurocognitive, neurobiological, and other at-risk health troubles.

4.1 Conclusion

In our judgment, the COVID-19 pandemic will have far reaching, long term impacts on children worldwide. Although some of these may be optimistic, we believe that the negative impacts will be shocking and could affect millions of children in some way. There is a need to ameliorate children and adolescents Access to mental health support services geared towards providing measures for developing healthy coping mechanisms during the current crisis. The outbreak of COVID-19 will also have a long-term and profound impact on older adults' health and well-being worldwide. Social isolation and being alone are likely to become major risk factors that affect older adults' health outcomes. Some strategies to address these issues can be implemented in several countries. These strategies include: raising awareness of the health and medical impact of social isolation and loneliness across the health care workforce and among members of the community; developing innovative technology based interventions to mobilize the resources from family members, community-based networks and resources that address social isolation and loneliness in older adults; and engaging the health care system to begin the process of developing methods to identify social isolation and loneliness in health concern settings.

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